

The Basic Teacher Competence in Applying Subject Integrated Guidance and Counseling Viewed from Work colleague's Control Locus and Resilience

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Abstract:- The research aimed at investigating and knowing the primary school teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service, and how this competence was influenced by primary school teacher's self internal (resilience and control locus) and external factor. This research was a descriptive qualitative one employing percentage calculation. The research subjects were 89 students. The student's data were obtained through the student problem identification scale and data on the student resilience were obtained by employing Resiliency Quotient Test. The research findings showed resiliency of large number of students (62,44%) were averagely on the level of below average, 27,77% on the level of average, and only 9,79% on the level of above average. The resilience aspects averagely dominance on the level of below average were self efficacy, reaching out, emotion regulation, empathy. The dominant aspect on the level of average was causal analysis, and there was no dominant aspect on the level of above average. It was concluded a large number of students needed resilient character up grading, by considering resiliency psychogram.

Keywords:- Basic Teacher Competence, Control Locus, Guidance Counseling, Resilience.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research was backed grounded by empirical conditions in basic education, community needs, and the laws or the government regulation of Republic of Indonesia related to guidance and counseling services for students or for the student character building. The guidance and counseling services in Indonesia schools were started in 1975 since guidance and counseling was included into formal school curriculum in junior/senior high school level, and extended to primary school level. The school operation prepares three areas, namely teaching learning process, management, and guidance counseling service. The guidance counseling service is psycho-educative and specific assistance through the shared services that aims to facilitate learning process and to make student personality mature accordance with their development.

The education and culture ministry regulation of Republic of Indonesia Number 111 year 2014 section 9, in the article 1 proposed that guidance counseling service in

education unit was performed by counselor or guidance counseling teacher. The responsibility of guidance counseling service practice was performed by counselor or guidance counseling teacher (article 2, section 9, the education and culture ministry regulation of Republic of Indonesia, number 111 Year 2014). These article 1 and article 2 showed that guidance counseling service was performed and taken responsibility by experts in the field of guidance counseling, called by counselor or guidance counseling teacher. Although there is any limitation faced, guidance counseling service in some particular senior high schools was still done by subject teacher.

In primary education level, guidance counseling service is given an assignment to subject teacher or homeroom teacher to implement it integrated with his role as subject teacher or classroom teacher. On the other word, there is no guidance counseling area expert especially sharing guidance counseling service to student like in senior high school. Based on decisions written on state ministry regulation of State Apparats Empowerment and Beuracracy Reformation (MENPAN) number 16 year 2009, article 13 determined classroom teacher activities in detail as many as 15 item. The item 1 decided that classroom teacher had an assignment to implement guidance and counseling in classroom as his responsibility. This statement explained that the guidance counseling program performer was classroom teacher.

However, the current guideline about guidance counseling service establishment in primary school based on education and culture ministry Regulation Number 111 year 2014, namely counselor and guidance counseling teacher. With faced limitations, indeed guidance counseling service implementation in basic school was ideally performed by collaborating with guidance counseling teacher or counselor (Culture and education ministry regulation of Republic of Indonesia Number 111 Year 2014 article 5, section 9). However, this in primary schools actually almost was not performed, because of primarily obstacles as follows: First, the teacher's knowledge about foundations of guidance counseling as well as guidance counseling work mechanism in primary school is still weak. Second, teacher realizes less the importance of guidance counseling for primary school student in building student potential optimal and character. Third, any difficulty to do cooperation with guidance counseling teacher from other school unit because no funding

for this. Fourth, basic school teacher's resilience to struggle overcoming difficult condition is not enough strong. Fifth, basic school teacher is less of orienting to internal locus control.

Five conditions above that were not enough strong supporting to be a competent primary school teacher apply subject integrated guidance counseling service and also is not enough strong to grow accurate efforts to be competent teacher, they are some reasons of the importance of analyzing the condition of empirical primary school teacher competence in primary school. Then this empirical data analysis result becomes base data a development follow up. As teacher staff in the faculty of education, Medan State University, specifically in department of Primary School Teacher Education (PGSD) at subject of Guidance counseling foundations, and when evaluating students's assignment result in basic education post graduate, Medan State University, writer discovered that guidance counseling service in primary school was not applied as a must by subject teacher and or homeroom teacher.

Observation result accompanied by writer's observation in technical doer unit (UPT) SD Negeri Number 067775, UPT SD Negeri Number 064034, UPT SD Negeri Number 067775 in milieu of Medan Johor district, Medan, North Sumatra were known that primary school teacher did not know so much about guidance counseling foundations, moreover applying them integratedly when teaching subject for student. Teacher interpreted and implemented guidance counseling service limited to give advice, to praise, to admonish and to warn students that breaks discipline rules, namely coming late to school, not completing school assignment at home, disturbing his learning friend, making classroom noisy, not joining in online learning. In the meantime, teacher can really integrate guidance counseling service when he teaches, namely sharing guidance on time management, ways to make friends, talking ethic, student's placement in study group, mediating fighting students. Guidance counseling service could be performed classically, group, and individually (Prayitno, 2004) according to problem in depth and primary school teacher's right. Guidance is prevention, or possibly problem solving.

The urgency of teacher competence practicing subject learning and in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service is placed on the role optimizing student's potential and facilitating student's learning fluency as well as assistance facilitating student's development in accordance with his development need. The child protective programs handling surrounding dangers independently were mostly needed. This was provided through guidance counseling service by subject teachers that has personal, social, pedagogical, and professional competences (look at Teacher Profession Education, Guidance Counseling materials, 2019).

Along with problem on lack of primary school teacher competence applying subject integrated guidance counseling service, writer founded that teacher's resilience in working and trying to become competence teacher was still low. This was supported by learning condition in era of pandemic and

post-pandemic covid-2019 that should learning programs be operationalized by online and/or offline, that needs do more than normal era learning. Teacher also faces variety of student's character who needs individual treatment and classical ones. There are order and discipline students, but there are also boring, uninterested to learn, unable to do online learning. This condition needs teacher's resilience to perform his function as teacher and an educator (pedagog, who serves guidance service for student).

Resilience was an universal capacity that makes person or community to be able to minimize or avoid of negative impact from these painful and sad events (Henderson & Milstein, 2003). Resilience is capacity to rise back, strong back successfully, although risk exposure is strong. Resilience is individual's capacity to adapt to the given difficulty situation, like facing challenges to apply subject integrated guidance counseling service. Menanti et al (2019) concluded that resilience was capacity, strength, resiliency, strong, struggle in facing challenge, unfavourable experiences, distress, and ability to adjust for difficulty situation. The urgency of resilience was placed upon resilience function for *overcoming, steering through, bouncing back, reaching out* (Reivich and Shatté, 2002).

The highly resilience is core psychological character that bases on possibly making the effort and can become competent teacher and counselor. On the other word, self competence in teaching and applying subject integrated guidance counseling service is influenced by teacher resilience strength. These teacher competence and resilience are influenced by self characteristic in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service, namely teacher's internal control locus. The internal control locus is meant is convince that something happened on self is result of self-behavior, not from external control or not because of fortunate. Internal control of locus is a conviction that things happened in self as consequence of self's action, not from external control, or not because of advantage.

This research focused on efforts of primary school teacher's competence development in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service as predicted still weak, through primary school teacher's resilience character analysis, in accordance with effort to achieve Indonesia National Education Goal (RPJP) (namely building human that has character); National Longterm Development Plan Year 2005-2025 (Indonesia Law Number 17 Year 2007, namely the shape of nation's character); vision, mission, goal of faculty of education, Medan State University); and the current research findings.

Vision of Medan State University is an excellence university in area of education, industry engineering, and culture. Medan State University has motto, "*The Character Building University*". Mission of Medan State University related to character is to build organization climate and healthy academic atmosphere, like owning resilience character in working, and the goal of Medan State University is to produce professional, character, excellence graduates, and owning an intellectual intelligence, entrepreneurship skill,

and nation perspective (Guideline Book of UNIMED 2019/2020). The strategic plan of UNIMED 2020-2024 was a break down RPJP UNIMED, with education field direction and policy was done through strategic such as inovation product reinforcement that can be used to lead in local, national, regional, and/or global level education changes.

II. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

- A. *How is the level of primary school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service holistically and based on its aspects?*
- B. *How is the level of primary school teacher’s resilience in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service holistically and based on its aspects?*
- C. *How is the level of primary school teacher’s internal control locus in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service?*

III. A REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

A. Definitions of Guidance and Counseling

According to Shertzer and Stones (1980), guidance was meant as an concept of efforts to facilitate individual, but as an educational construct, referring to a form of experience that can help student understanding himselfes, and as a program, guidance refers to an organized procedure and process to reach particular personal and education goal (Surya, 1988). Surya (1988) articulated guidance as process providing assistance continuously and systematically from counselor to counselee in order to achieve independence in self-understanding, self-acceptance, self-direction and self-actualization in achieving the optimal development level and self-adaptation to environment.

The word, ‘guidance’ is often faired with the word, counseling. Counseling is follow up action of guidance activity for client who need counseling, although the guidance and counseling activities can stand on independently. The other opinion told that counseling was part of guidance service. This was proposed by Nayak (1997: 3) that told that “*Guidance is a term which is broader than counselling and which includes counselling as one of its services*”.

Guidance handles simple problems, and can be done by non expertise personnel as far as overcoming guidance substance. Besides that, it is critical to be equipped with knowledge and skill about pedagogic. Meanwhile, counseling could just be performed by an expert and handling deepen problems and therapeutically. According to McLeod (2003): “Counselling includes work wih individuals and with relationships which may be developmental, crisis support, psychotherapeutic, guiding or problem solving... The task of counselling is to give the ‘client’ an opportunity to explore, discover and clarify ways of living more satisfyingly and resourcefully” (BAC, 1984). “Counselling denotes a

professional relationship between a trained counsellor and a client... This relationship is usually person-to-person, although it may sometimes involve more than two people. It is desgnd to help clients to understand and clarify their views of their lifespace, and to learn to reach their self-determined goals through meaningful, well-informed choices and through resolution of problems of an emotional or interpersonal nature” (Burks and Stefflre, 1979: 14).

The citation above showed that counseling activity includes working with individuals and relating that possibly characterizes self-development, support to crisis, psychotherapeutic, guidance or problem solving. The task of counseling provides opportunity for clients to explore, find and describe a more satisfied and smart life ways. Counseling indicates the professional relationship between a trained counselor and client. This relationship usually characterizes individu to individu, although sometime involving more than one person. Counseling is designed to facilitate client understanding and describing their view of life, and facilitates to achieve their self-decision goal through choice that has been well-informed as well as meaningfull for them, and through emotional and interpersonal character problem solving (Burk and Stefflre, 1970:14).

Pine and Boy (1968: 51 in Menanti, 2015) differentiated counseling and guidance based on different area in process, *locus of attention, goal, size of group, leader’s orientation*. It can be looked at table 1

TABLE 1: BASIC DIFFERENCE BETWEEN COUNSELING AND GUIDANCE

Area of Difference	Counseling	Guidance
Process	Affective	Cognitives
Locus of attention	The Person	Information
Goal	Self actualization	Increased knowledge
Size of group	One to eigft	Unlimited
Leader’s orientation	Therapeutic	Informational

Pine and Boy’s opinion (1968: 51) above could be understood that core of counseling that differentiates it from guidance primarily to affective process (feeling, emotion), therapeutic orientation (giving assistance to solve problem), full attention on person. Meanwhile, the core of guidance tends on cognitive process aiming to promote knowledge, and informative to one person up to mass (unlimited time).

B. Position and Functions of Guidance and Counseling in School

Guidance counseling service in school is one of three elements prepared by school. It can clearer be looked at picture 1 as follows:

Fig 1: Position of Guidance Counseling in School

Nayak (1997) proposed three functions of guidance counseling, such as adjustment, orientational, and developmental ones. At the adjustment function, Guidance counseling service facilitates students to be able to adapt themselves to situation in school, at home, and community. At the orientation function, guidance counseling service facilitates students directing the coming values and plans. Meanwhile, at the development function, Guidance counseling service facilitates students to be able to complete

The functions of guidance counseling are broadest, covering a variety of problems and aimed to many parties. In this case, it is critical controlled that professional guidance counseling teacher's role and function are different of teacher or non teacher who have'nt guidance counseling expertise background, where their right does not perform counseling, but limited to providing guidance service, namely providing basic services such as giving information. Meanwhile, guidance counseling teacher or professional counselor has four competences of guidance counseling, namely basic service, responsive service, individual planning, and system supporting (Work Guideline of Teacher Education Training of Guidance Counseling, No Year).

C. Educator's Competence

Educator's competence covered four competences, such as personal, social, pedagogical, and professional competences (PPG-BK material, 2019). The personal competence indicated teacher/educator's skill performing as mature, friendly personal, accept student as he is, fond of helping to solve other's problem, able to creating convenience feeling for students. Social competence was educator/teacher's skill like able to communicate with others, able to build good communication, and able to maintain interpersonal relationship, and etc. Pedagogical competence was skill using the student educating and guiding method, like overcoming to guide student classically applied the lecturing method, guiding individually by applying rapport (approach, building good relationship). The professional competence was mastery of the educating or guiding substances in accordance with its substance.

their developmental tasks in order to not appearing problem. And if it has appeared problem, then guidance counseling service facilitates students solving their problem. Role statement-The School Counselor by American School Counselor Association as elaborated by Gibson and Mitchell (1990) proposed that counselor was a certified professional paedagog that facilitates student, teachers, parent, and administrators. It is also proposed that counselor facilitates counseling process, consultation, and coordination.

D. Resilience

The term, "resilience" is adopted by many experts to describe phenomena such as *invulnerable, invincible, hardy*. Resilience is process to overcome, change, and identify any difficulty experienced by individu by responding negative situation with health intellectual function and good social support (Richardson, 2002). Resilience was competence to bounce back, strong back successfully, although risk exposure gets strong. Resilience is a person's capacity to adjust or adapt to the faced difficulty situation, like facing challenge applies subject integrated guidance counseling service. Menanti et al (2019) concluded that resilience was competence, strongness, tenacity, strength, struggle, in facing the challenge, unfavourable experience, distress, and ability to adapt for the difficulty situation.

The high resilience is core psychology character that possibly underlines teacher's primary school to effort and can become competence teacher and counselor. On the other word, self-competence in teaching and applying subject integrated guidance counseling service is influenced by teacher's resilience strenght. Teacher's competence or resilience in applying this subject integrated guidance counseling service were influenced by self-characteristics such as teacher's internal control locus.

Resilience was built from 7 aspects, such as *emotion regulation, impulse control, optimism, causal analysis, empathy, self efficacy, reaching out* (Reivich and Shatté (2002). This resilience was result from some internal or external factors (Pidgeon et al, 2014). Henderson and Milstein (2003) adapted from Richardson *et al.* 1990; Benard, 1991; Werner and Smith, 1992; Hawkins, Catalano and Miller, 1992, about external and individual characteristics.

Individual characteristics were partly having the internal control locus, valued meaning, self-confidence, autonomy, independence, able to control emotional drives, social competence. Those external characteristics were partly existing familiar interaction style, not judging, leadership, significant participating chance, expressing realistically and high success expectation, developing altruism values, helping seriously.

Resilience is increased through aspects shaping it, such as, *emotion regulation, impuls control, optimism, causal analysis, empathy, self efficacy, and reaching out*. It can also be done by increasing the individual characteristic supporting resilient personal and external factors determining resiliency. The used way varies, such as giving information, giving content service, giving group guidance, training, and giving specific counseling service for a weak resiliency related to the intense personal problems.

The urgency of resilience was placed on the resilience function for *overcoming, steering through, bouncing back, reaching out* (Reivich and Shatté, 2002). *Overcoming* meant that with resilience owned, person can handles or prevents defeatable problems. *Steering through* meant that with resilience owned, person can control themselves in facing his problems and can precedes those problem well. *Bounceback* implied that with resilience owned, person can be back fastly toward normal condition after he experienced the difficult events; and *reaching out* is that with resilience owned, person could overcome problem solving on the distress snd traumatic events and taking lesson learned from the experience (Menanti et al, 2019).

E. Control Locus

Control locus consisted of *internal locus of control* and *external locus of control*. Internal Locus of control convinced

that signal and events happened depended upon a lot of efforts and competences, but external locus of control signed to lucky, destiny (Stratton and Hayes, 1993). Internal Locus of control is convinced what action results depended upon what to make, and external locus of control convinced that action results were an events/incidences out of self-control.

Teacher having internal locus of control viewed that how his competence in performing subject integrated guidance counseling service under self control of his hardwork effort, but teacher having external locus of control viewed that his competence in guidance counseling service depended upon efforts contributed by persons out of his self to build his competence.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This research used qualitative approach to know on level of each research variables and to know the effect of independence variable on the dependence variable, included with narrative descriptions.

B. Research Variable

The independent variable of this research is:
 1) The primary school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service, teacher’s internal control of locus, on the dependence variable: teacher resilience at work.
 2) The teacher resilience at work on the dependence variable: primary school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service.

Below was pictured the picture of reseach fish bone:

Fig 2: Picture of Research Fishborne.
 * : Cause 3 dan Cause 4 were not researched

The above skeleton showed that primary school teacher’s competence in the field plays role as teacher. Teacher also plays role as a paedagog (educator) who is providing subject integrated guidance counseling service. The teacher competence correlates or is influenced by internal and external factors, as explained as follows:

- Primary school teacher who has low work resilience, is less encouraged
- to become competence teacher in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service. The contrary thing happened. Primary school teacher who has external control locus, is less encouraged to become competence teacher in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service. The contrary thing happened.
- Resilience as weak primarily character, primary school teacher is less encouraged to become competence teacher in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service.

- Resilience, internal control locus positively affect partially and simultaneously on primary school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance counseling service

C. Reseach Data Collection

Data is collected through primary school teacher via face to face meeting and when needed, it is equipped by offline. The data collecting instrument used Likert scale arranged by himself and adapted from the existing instrument. To complete data obtained through scale, it was used checklist to put the observation result data included with interview to some teachers representing UPT SD.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis was established with percentage calculation and effect test.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Summary Of Research Variable Findings

Number	Variable/ Sub Variable	Very high	High	Middle	Less	Low
1	Primary school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service holistically.			X		
	- Personal aspect			X		
	- Social aspect			X		
	- Pedagogical aspect				X	
	- Professional aspect			X		
2	Primary school teacher’s work resilience in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service, holistically		X			
	- Aspect of emotional regulation			X		
	- Aspect of impulse control		X			
	- Aspect of optimism		X			
	- Aspect of causal analysis		X			
	- Aspect of empathy		X			
	- Aspect of self efficacy		X			
	- Aspect of Reaching out		X			
3	School teacher’s Internal Control Locus		X			

At each research variables, generally included to the middle level were only to the variable of basic school teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service (variable Y). The existence to the middle level with average score 2,929 meant that teacher’s knowledge and skill in performing subject integrated guidance counseling service to student in school, either inside

classroom learning activities or outside classroom learning, were included at the middle. But two other variables, such as variable of teacher’s work resilience in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service (variable X1), variable of internal control locus (X2), generally were included high.

Based on the profile generally consisting of those three research variables, views clearly that the lowest variable is at variable of teacher’s competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service. Hereby, this teacher competence variable needed quality development priority in implementing subject integrated guidance and counseling service, primarily to the pedagogical competence aspect that exists on the average score 2,348. Then next to priority on professional competence aspect that exists on average score 2,662, personal competence aspect that exists

on average score 3,321, and social competence aspect that exists on average score 3,385.

Meanwhile two primarily variables X (independence variables), needs development regularly were teacher’s internal control locus variable (existing on average score 3,4970), teacher’s work resilience variable in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service (existing on average score 3,666).

Departure from each aspect of variable X (dependence variable) above can be explained as follows:

- Primary school teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service Primary school teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service averagely was in general categorized middle. But based on its aspects it was known that personal, social, and professional aspects were categorized middle, and only pedagogical aspect was categorized low. Primary school teacher's work resilience level in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service (variable X1) Departure from research findings showing that primary school teacher's work resilience in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service, holistically averagely were included high (existing on average score 3,666), and based on teacher's work resilience aspects categorized middle is only to emotional regulation aspect (existing on average score 2,975), But these six other aspects (Such as Impulse control, Optimism, Causal analysis, empathy, Self-efficacy, and Reaching out were categorized high, so primary school teacher's resilience profile in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service needs development follow up of resilience aspects with priority scale as follows: emotional regulation (existing on average score 2,975), self-efficacy (existing on average score 3,398), reaching out (existing on average score 3,734), empathy (existing on emotional regulation aspects (Existing on average score 3,975).
- Primary school teacher's internal control locus level Research finding indicating primary school teacher's internal control locus averagely categorized high (existing on average score 3,497) is strength encouraging teacher to strike studying independently about how subject integrated guidance and counseling service be implemented, although with limited human

Looking at level existing profile of these research variables, appears an idea that why with two variables considered associating to or can influences teacher's competence in performing subject integrated guidance and counseling service, positively, but teacher's averagely competence in performing subject integrated guidance and counseling service was only categorized as middle. The condition like this can be caused by teacher strength within internal and external factors influencing the competence in performing subject integrated guidance and counseling service, still latent strength appearing not yet manifest maximally to factual competence in implementing subject integrated guidance and counseling service. Not manifested to be because of less of learning resources that teacher can employ, either human learning resources, or learning resources such as book, social media on guidance and counseling. Obstacle can also comes from teacher's economical factor to develop himself, and Factor of less maximal of positively external distress that obliges teacher implementing and reporting performance on subject integrated guidance and counseling service.

resources/expert in milieu of basic school as working place and surrounding. The level of highly internal control locus makes teacher learning on self-initiative, not waiting for encouragement or upper suggestions or other external party. Teacher builds its success depending primarily upon their efforts.

Profile that variable X averagely is categorized high, but variable Y just has middle competence as mentioned, can be valuable as follows:

- If viewed from variable of teacher's work resilience (variable X1), then it can be told that teacher has competence facing challenge and adaptable in difficulty situation when applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service (variable X1), although its competence (variable Y) averagely is only categorized middle. Work resilience owned by primary school teacher in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service categorized on high is strength for guidance and counseling service development. The other research done by Mataro (2021) to 84 teachers in SMA Negeri 2 Medan showed that teacher's resilience in working was only categorized middle
- If viewed from internal control locus owned by teacher (variable X2), then teacher has view that success and failure happened, for instance, in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service were result of his efforts striking hard, seriously or failure is result of his less of strength to strike hard. Teacher did not consider that reach of achievement or failure (like in term of competence to apply subject integrated guidance and counseling service) is destiny or fate or caused by external factor. With teacher's strong internal control locus, hopefully will directs teacher's behavior emphasizing himself in obtaining achievement or implementing guidance and counseling service.

It is important to do intervention and environment to increase teacher's knowledge and skill competence transformed by the other relevance expert like technology expert to provide guidance and counseling service employing the interesting technology like employing videos. Then next to teacher's mentoring in performing subject integrated guidance and counseling service.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the study answers two research questions on the primary school teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service viewed from work colleague's control locus and resilience in milieu of Gedung Johor. The first finding showed that (1) Primary school teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service, was generally averagely categorized middle. But based on its aspects, it was known that personal, social, and professional aspects were categorized as middle. Only on pedagogical aspect was categorized as low. The second finding shows that (2) Primary teacher's work resilience in applying subject integrated guidance and counseling service was generally categorized high. But based on its aspects it is known that from seven

aspects, there were highly categorized six aspect, such as aspects of *impulse control, optimism, causal analysis, self efficacy, and reaching out*. Aspect categorized middle is *emotion regulation*. The third finding showed that (3) Primary school Teacher's *internal locus of control*) was categorized high.

REFERENCES

- [1]. *Buku Pedoman Universitas Negeri Medan Tahun 2013-2014*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [2]. Gibson, R. L. & Mitchell, M. H. 1995. *Introduction to Counselling and Guidance*. New Jersey: Merrill, an Imprint of Prentice Hall.
- [3]. Henderson, N. & Milstein, M. M. 2003. *Resiliency in School: Making It Happen for Students and Educators*. California: Corwin Press, Inc
- [4]. Luthans, F. 2005. *Organizational Behavior*. Tenth Edition. Boston: McGraw-H
- [5]. Materi Bimbingan dan Konseling. 2019. [6].
- [6]. McLeod, J. 2003. *An Introduction Counselling*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- [7]. McShane, S. L. & Glinov, M. A. V. 2003. *Organizational Behavior*. Second Edition. Boston: McGraw-Hill Irwin
- [8]. Menanti, A. 2019. *Analisis Peran Konselor Sebaya dalam Peningkatan Resiliensi Mahasiswa Bermasalah pada Prodi BK FIP UNIMED*. Medan: UNIMED.
- [9]. _____. 2015. *Karakter Konselor Profesional Aktual dan Ideal Mahasiswa Prodi [9] Bimbingan dan Konseling FIP UNIMED Berbasis Standarisasi Pakar*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [10]. Nayak, A. K. 1997. *Guidance and Counselling*. New Delhi: APH Publishing Corporation.
- [11]. Reivich, K. & Shatté, A. 2002. *The Resilience Factor: 7 Essential Skills for Overcoming Life's Inevitable Obstacles*. New York: Random House, Inc.
- [12]. Richardson, G. E. 2002. The Metatheory of Resilience and Resiliency. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 58 (3), 307-321. DOI: 10.1002/jelp.10020. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11836712>. Diakses Tanggal 27 Oktober 2016.
- [13]. Pedoman Pelaksanaan Pendidikan Profesi Guru Bimbingan dan Konseling atau Konselor. Tanpa Tahun.
- [14]. Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Budaya RI Nomor 111 Tahun 2014 tentang *Bimbingan dan Konseling pada Pendidikan Dasar dan Pendidikan Menengah*.
- [15]. Peraturan Menteri Negara Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara dan Reformasi Birokrasi Nomor 16 tahun 2009.
- [16]. Pidgeon, Aileen M., et al. 2014. Examining Characteristics of Resilience Among University Students: An International Study. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 2014, 2, 14-22. Published Online November 2014 in SciRes. <http://www.scrip.org/journal/iss>. Diakses Tanggal 22 Januari 2017.
- [17]. Prayitno. 2004. *Layanan Informasi*. Padang: Jurusan Bimbingan dan Konseling Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Padang.
- [18]. Santrock, J. W. 2008. *Psikologi Pendidikan*.
- [19]. Shelfzer, B. & Stone, S. C. (1980). *Fundamentals of Counselling*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- [20]. Surya, M. 1988. *Dasar-Dasar Penyuluhan (Konseling)*. Jakarta: Departemen P dan K Dirjen Dikti PPLPTK.
- [21]. Straton, P., Hayes, N. 1993. *A Students Dictionary of Psychology*. Bristol: J. W. Arrowsmith Ltd.
- [22]. Undang-Undang RI Nomor 17 Tahun 2007 tentang *Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Panjang Nasional Tahun 2005-2025*.
- [23]. Wirawan. 2014. *Kepemimpinan: Teori, Psikologi, Perilaku Organisasi, Aplikasi dan Penelitian*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.